

Oxidation of hydrocarbons, cyclic alcohols and aldehydes by *in situ* prepared sodium ferrate

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Abstract : *In situ* prepared sodium ferrate was used for the oxidation of structurally different hydrocarbons, cyclic alcohols and aldehydes thus eliminating the tedious process of separating potassium ferrate in the solid form before its use as an oxidant. Montmorillonite K10 under microwave irradiations catalyzed the oxidations resulting in the excellent yields. Maximum yields of the products under controlled conditions were obtained by changing the reaction conditions one by one keeping other factors constant which may affect the yield. The system is simple, proceeds without over-oxidation under reported conditions and in some cases gives even better results compared to potassium ferrate oxidations. Phenanthrene was oxidized to 9-fluorenone (86.1%) instead of phenanthraquinone. Ferrate oxidations are environmentally benign and being very fast under microwave irradiations, become economical also.

Keywords : Sodium ferrate, montmorillonite K10, microwaves, oxidation, 9-fluorenone.

Introduction

Oxidation is one of the most fundamental tools for organic transformations and there has been enormous activity in the development of new reagents. There has been sporadic interest in the use of the potassium ferrate, K_2FeO_4 , for the oxidation of organic substrates¹ because of its potential to deliver an environmentally acceptable, non-toxic alternative to the conventional reagent systems. Inorganic oxidations by potassium ferrate have been the current area of interest of many workers^{2,3}. There have been reports on the oxidation of alcohols using potassium ferrate under a range of conditions^{4,5}.

Iron(VI) is a selective and powerful two electron oxidant and can prevent over oxidation for a large number of organic compounds with Fe^{III} as a by-product and therefore has a role in cleaner technology for organic synthesis. Use of sodium or potassium ferrates is associated with the problem of their separation in the solid forms, which requires tedious processes. This problem may be tackled if ferrate ion is adsorbed on micro porous adsorbent which also catalyzes the oxidation and the system then acts efficiently for organic oxidations with high selectivity. Heterogeneous organic reactions have proven useful to chemists both in academia and in industry. Clay-

catalyzed organic transformations have generated considerable interest because of their inexpensive nature and special catalytic attributes under heterogeneous reaction conditions⁶⁻⁸.

Use of microwaves as a non-conventional energy source for activation of reactions is a popular and useful technology^{9,10}. The combination of microwave irradiation with montmorillonite K10 leads to enhanced reaction rates, higher yields of pure products, easier work-up and, sometimes, to selective conversions with several advantages of the eco-friendly approach in the framework of green chemistry¹¹.

We have reported earlier oxidation of aromatic alcohols and aldehydes by iron ferrate¹². In the present study *in situ* prepared sodium ferrate adsorbed on montmorillonite K10 was used for oxidizing various organics. *In situ* prepared sodium ferrate-montmorillonite K10 system eliminates the tedious process of separating potassium ferrate in solid form before its use as an oxidant, the common process which has been followed by a large number of workers. Various organic substrates selected were difficult to oxidize hydrocarbons, cyclic alcohols, aldehydes and amines. Product yield under microwave irradiation was compared with that obtained under traditional heat-

ing and at room temperature also. It was observed that in certain oxidations better yields were obtained compared to those obtained by using potassium ferrate as an oxidant.

Results and discussion

The reactions were complete within a few minutes in microwave oven. For getting the maximum yield 4 to 6 sets were performed by changing the concentration or conditions of each variable which can affect the yield. Table 1 shows the sample variation of various factors and their effect on the yield of 2-methyl cyclohexanone. In a control experiment organic substrate pre-adsorbed on montmorillonite, was added to the aqueous solution of ferric nitrate (entry 1, Table 1) and sodium hypochlorite solution (entry 2, Table 1) separately under similar conditions and the paste thus formed was irradiated in microwave oven.

Negligible amount of product formed showed that ferric nitrate and sodium hypochlorite individually were not responsible for oxidation and the system functions properly only under optimum conditions. Yield increased with increasing power of microwaves (entries 3 and 4, Table 1) apparently due to the availability of more energy required to facilitate the reaction. While increase in the time of exposure increases the yield in the beginning, reaches to a maximum and beyond which further increase in time decreases the yield (entries 4, 5 and 6, Table 1). This was probably due to the vaporation of product due to excess heating under prolonged exposure. Yield reaches to a maximum and then starts decreasing with further increase in the amount of ferric nitrate (entries 7, 4 and

8, Table 1) while yield decreases with increasing amount of sodium hypochlorite (entries 4 and 9, Table 1). Probable reason for this appears to be the decomposition of ferrate ions due to the presence of traces of impurities the reactants. It has been shown that the half life of an alkaline ferrate solution is reduced by a factor of at least 40 when nickel(II) is added in micromolar concentration^{13,14}. The charged layered structure of the aluminosilicate solid may provide a suitable and highly polar environment to adsorb organic substrate and to favour its encounter with ferrate ions in the hydrated interlamellar spaces which has a catalyzing effect on the rate of oxidation of organics. It has been suggested¹⁵ that aluminosilicate solid acts as a source of humidity and also displays an intrinsic catalytic activity, which is not due to the intervention of strong Brønsted or Lewis acidic centers present within the aluminosilicate structure. *In situ* prepared sodium ferrate, in certain cases, proved to be a better oxidant compared to potassium ferrate as oxidation of cyclohexane with *in situ* prepared sodium ferrate under microwave irradiation (150 s) and traditional heating (180 min) resulted in 17.9 to 19.8% yield of cyclohexanone respectively with no formation of cyclohexanol compared to 14% yield of the mixture of cyclohexanone and cyclohexanol (in 72 h with product distribution of 51 : 49) as reported by Delude¹⁵. In another case, apart from the electronic effects, better yields at 30.8 and 34.2% of 2-methyl cyclohexanone were obtained from 2-methyl cyclohexanol under microwave irradiation (150 s) and traditional heating (180 min) compared to the reported yield of 26% of cyclohexanone from cyclohexanol (in 24 h) when potassium ferrate was used as an oxidant¹⁵. Pres-

Table 1. Effect of various factors on yield of 2-methyl cyclohexanone obtained from 2-methyl cyclohexanol (2.0 mmol)

Entry no.	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ ·9H ₂ O (mmol)	NaClO (mmol)	Montmorillonite K10 (g)	MW (% Power)	Time (s)	Yield (%)
1	4.49	-	2.0	80	120	Negligible
2	-	26.4	2.0	80	120	Negligible
3	4.95	26.4	2.0	20	120	13.7
4	4.95	26.4	2.0	80	120	29.9
5	4.95	26.4	2.0	80	90	18.8
6	4.95	26.4	2.0	80	150	29.9
7	4.45	26.4	2.0	80	120	25.7
8	5.44	26.4	2.0	80	120	27.4
9	4.95	32.3	2.0	80	120	23.9

Table 2. Extent of oxidation of various organic compounds with Na₂FeO₄ adsorbed on Montmorillonite K10

Organic substrate = 2.0 mmol, Montmorillonite K10 = 2.0 g (a-h); in the absence of MMT (i-1). Fe(NO₃)₃.9H₂O (mmol) = 4.95 (a, b, g-l); 7.42 (c-f). NaClO (mmol) = 29.4 (a, g-l); 26.4 (b); 44.0 (c); 36.7 (d-f). Microwave power = 80% (a-h), instantaneous reaction (i-l)

Organic substrate	Product	Time (s)	Yield (isolated yield in mg) (%)
Cyclopentanol (a)	Cyclopentanone (a')	120	7.5 (40) ^a , 26.5 (140) ^b , 32.1 (170) ^c
2-Methyl cyclohexanol (b)	2-Methyl cyclohexanone (b')	120	10.2 (60) ^a , 30.8 (180) ^b , 34.2 (200) ^c
Cyclohexane (c)	Cyclohexanone (c')	150	8.9 (50) ^a , 17.9 (100) ^b , 19.8 (110) ^c
Ethyl benzene (d)	Acetophenone (d')	150	10.0 (60) ^a , 33.3 (200) ^b , 36.6 (220) ^c
Anthracene (e)	9,10-Anthraquinone (e')	150	24.0 (50) ^a , 62.5 (130) ^b , 96.1 (200) ^c
Phenanthrene (f)	9-Fluorenone (f')	180	44.4 (160) ^a , 69.4 (250) ^b , 86.1 (310) ^c
4-Methoxy benzaldehyde (g)	4-Methoxy benzoic acid (g')	120	0.0 (0) ^a , 13.1 (40) ^b , 19.7 (60) ^c
4-Hydroxy benzaldehyde (h)	4-Hydroxy benzoic acid (h')	120	0.0 (0) ^a , 72.4 (100) ^b , 86.9 (120) ^c
Diphenyl amine (i)	Polydiphenylamine (i')	-	Polymerized
Cyclohexyl amine (j)	Polycyclohexylamine (j')	-	Polymerized
2,4-Dinitroaniline (k)	Poly-2,4-dinitroaniline (k')	-	Polymerized
Aniline hydrochloric acid (l)	Polyaniline (l')	-	Polymerized

a; Oxidation at room temperature (~28–30 °C) in 48 h, b; oxidation in presence of K10 under MW irradiation, c; oxidation in water bath with K10 [in 3 h (a-f) and 1 h (g and h)].

ence of electron donating (-CH₃, -OCH₃) or abstracting (-OH) groups, in the usual manner, decreased or increased the yields respectively (entries a, b, g and h, Table 2). It was also observed that polymerization takes place if amino group is present in the benzene or in the cyclic rings (entries i to l, Table 2). Oxidation of phenanthrene resulted in 9-fluorenone. Probable path of oxidation is given in Scheme 1. Oxidation of phenanthrene generally results in the formation of 9,10-phenanthraquinone which on warming with alkali undergoes benzylic rearrangement and finally gives 9-fluorenone in heating conditions¹⁶ through the formation of 9-hydroxyfluorene-9-carboxylic acid. Solid support can be recycled 2 to 4 time with only 5 to 10% decrease in the efficiency in each cycle.

Experimental

Material and methods :

Analytical grade reagents were used as received without further purification. Montmorillonite K10 (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany, surface area : 220–270 m²/g), ferric nitrate, sodium hypochlorite, alumina, silica gel, diethyl ether were of E. Merck grade. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Reactions under microwave irradiations were studied in a Kenstar oven (model OM-20 ESP, 800 W, Aurangabad, India). FTIR measurements were taken with a Bruker Vertex-70 IR spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra with a Xeol 400 MHz

spectrophotometer in CDCl₃ with TMS as internal standard. Reactions were monitored by TLC with Merck GF 254 silica gel coated plates in which no product other than the reported could be found. Purity and identification of products were confirmed by taking m.p. of the product or its 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives, by running TLC plates with authentic samples and spectral studies.

Preparation of sodium ferrate :

Without following the tedious and lengthy process of separating and purifying iron ferrate firstly in the solid state, the present study was performed to see the oxidizing efficiency of iron(VI) in combination with montmorillonite K10 in the oxidations of organic compounds. For this purpose sodium ferrate was prepared by taking ferric nitrate (Fe(NO₃)₃.9H₂O) 2.0 g (4.49 mmol) in a 50 ml flask and the required amount of sodium hypochlorite solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. Formation of a clear dark purple-red coloured solution indicates the formation of ferrate dianions¹⁷.

General procedure for performing the reaction :

Calculated quantity of organic substrate adsorbed on MMT K10 was mixed with freshly prepared sodium ferrate (Na₂FeO₄) solution and the mixture was irradiated in a domestic microwave oven for the required time. In solution phase reactions mixture kept in a flask fitted with

condenser was heated in a water bath for the required time. After completion of the reaction, both in the solid as well as in the solution phase, the reaction mixture was acidified with 2 N H₂SO₄ solution and was extracted with appropriate solvent (3 × 20 ml). Extract was evaporated under reduced pressure to afford the product.

Characterization of products :

Cyclopentanone (a') was prepared from cyclopentanol and analyzed in the form of its 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone. M.p. of hydrazone was 143 °C (reported 146 °C); ¹H NMR δ : 11.04 (1H, s), 9.43 (1H, s), 7.08–8.36 (2H, m), 2.07–2.34 (4H, q), 1.26–1.58 (4H, q). 2-Methyl cyclohexanone (b') was prepared from 2-methyl cyclohexanol (2.0 mmol). M.p. of hydrazone was 135 °C (reported 137 °C); ¹H NMR δ : 11.04 (1H, s), 9.43 (1H, s), 7.26–8.32 (2H, m), 1.35–2.85 (9H, m), 1.20–1.28 (3H, q). Cyclohexanone (c') was prepared from cyclohexane (2.0 mmol) in the similar way. M.p. of hydrazone was 161 °C (reported 162 °C); ¹H NMR δ : 11.20 (1H, s), 9.13 (1H, s), 7.96–8.31 (2H, m), 2.45–2.50 (4H, q), 1.71–1.80 (6H, q). Acetophenone (d') was prepared from ethylbenzene (2.0 mmol). M.p. of hydrazone was 247 °C (reported 250 °C); ¹H NMR δ : 11.33 (1H, s), 9.16 (1H, s), 7.26–8.77 (7H, m), 1.55 (3H, s). 9,10-Anthraquinone (e') was prepared from anthracene (1.0 mmol). M.p. of product was 284 °C (reported 286 °C); IR ν_{max} : 1673 (ν_{C=O}), 3080 (ν_{C-H}, str. arom.), 696, 725, 882 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C-H}, arom. bend.). 9-Fluorenone (f') was prepared from phenanthrene (1.0 mmol). M.p. of product was 83 °C (reported 82–85 °C); ¹H NMR δ : 7.24–8.70 (8H, m); IR ν_{max} : 1671 (ν_{C=O}), 3057 (ν_{C-H}, str. arom.), 756, 866, 881 (ν_{C-H}, bend. arom.), 1600 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C=C}, str. arom.). 4-Methoxybenzoic acid (g') was prepared from 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (2.0 mmol). M.p. of product was 184 °C (reported 186 °C); IR ν_{max} : 2500 to 3100 (ν_{-OH} and ν_{C-H} stretch), 1686 (ν_{C=O}), 1270 and 1176 (ν_{C-O}, str.), 1600 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C=C}, str. arom.). 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid (h') was prepared from 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.0 mmol). M.p. of product was 213 °C (reported 215 °C); IR ν_{max} : 2500 to 3300 (broad ν_{-OH} and ν_{C-H}, stretch), 1684 (ν_{C=O}), 1267 and 1155 (ν_{C-O}, str.), 3608 (ν_{O-H}, str. arom.), 1600 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C=C}, str. arom.). Diphenyl amine (i), cyclohexyl amine (j), 2,4-dinitroaniline (k) and aniline hydrochloric acid (l), under the reaction conditions, polymerize within few minutes at room temperature without

exposing the mixture to microwaves or heating in a water bath.

Scheme 1. Conversion of phenanthrene to 9-fluorenone.

Conclusion :

Present study shows that strong oxidizing capacity of *in situ* prepared sodium ferrate is at par with that of potassium ferrate with the added advantage that tedious and lengthy process of separation of potassium ferrate in the solid form before its use as an oxidant is completely eliminated. In conclusion, we have developed a rapid and efficient microwave-assisted procedure for the synthesis of various organic compounds using sodium ferrate as a novel oxidant.

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